

Once Upon a Time, There was a Terms of Service

a moment at DRS Festival of Emergence 2021

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Session 1: Introduction | September 6, 2021 | CEST 10:00

24/7 access

Session 2: Reflections | September 17, 2021 | CEST 11:00

Tools: Miro, Reverb.chat, Zoom

PhD project on

Democratic Data Governance: Designing Alternatives for the Terms of Service

UMEÅ INSTITUTE OF DESIGN
UMEÅ UNIVERSITY

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**in 2021, in average,
we have 40 to 60 apps on our phones,
which means that we have “interacted with”
40 to 60 Terms of Service networks.**

“

In 2008

two Carnegie Mellon professors calculated that

a reasonable reading of all the privacy policies

that one encounters in a year would require

76 full workdays

at a national opportunity cost of

\$781 billion.

Zuboff, S. (2019). The age of surveillance capitalism: the fight for the future at the new frontier of power. London: Profile Books.

**Seriously,
who has the time to read any ToSs
who gets what they are saying**

35 minutes, 18 seconds

A screenshot of a sign-up form for Miro. The form contains two unchecked checkboxes: "I agree to Miro Terms and Privacy Policy." and "I agree to receive Miro news and updates." Below the checkboxes is a blue button labeled "Get started now". Five purple arrows originate from the "Terms" and "Privacy Policy" text in the first checkbox and point to labels for "Support Policy", "Security Policy", "Documentation", "DPA", and "Cookies Policy" arranged in an arc to the right of the form.

**But, we like it or not, one way or another,
from the second we take a peek on any digital service,
we all interact with these ToSs.**

**This moment is about creating a collection of these experiences and
moreover provoking us in envisioning future experiences.**

How to Participate in this Moment?

- 1 Think about your past experiences with or your future visions of Terms of Service(s).
Is there anything you would like to share?

CREATIVE STORYTELLING

- | me and my ToSs | a day in the life of a ToS | the ToS family | ToS on the News |
- | ToS applied to the analog life | your favorite TV show where ToS is a “topic” |

How to Participate in this Moment?

1 Some questions that might help you to start thinking:

How do you feel about ToSs in general?

What are your habits around ToSs? What kind of changes have you gone through?

Do you remember first time you saw a ToS or days without a ToS?

Have you read any ToSs? What was the impact on you?

Have you ever changed your mind about a digital service after reading a ToS?

Have you ever contacted the company asking question about their terms?

Have you exercised a special right mentioned on a ToS?

Do you ever compare digital and analog experiences? Where are ToSs in this comparison?

Have you read or heard any interesting interaction or speculation of ToSs?

How do you see your experience with ToSs in 5,10, 20 or more years?

Will it be any different? Should it be any different? Good different or bad different?

Is there a ToS in the future that you interact with personally?

How to Participate in this Moment?

2 Once your story is ready, visit [Reverb.chat](https://record.reverb.chat) to record it.

Practical Details

The Link: <https://record.reverb.chat/>

Create an account if you would like to have better control over your recordings.

But you can also use the platform without an account.

You can only record for maximum 10 minutes. After 10 minutes, the recording automatically stops.

You can create several recordings.

Once you are finished with your recording, give it a title and save it.

How to Participate in this Moment?

- 3 Copy the embed code and come back to Miro. Select a frame that fits to your story's character. Paste the embed code, fill in the details on the frame, place your story dot on the spectrum.

How to Participate in this Moment?

4 Interact with the content.

Listen to the other stories.

Leave comments if you like.

Join the second Zoom session on the 17th of September at 11:00 (CEST) to reflect on the stories and discuss.

What will I Do with your Contributions and Data?

As stated, this is part of my PhD project. So, I would like to keep the contributions as insights and for further study. If and/or when I want to use your contributions in written, oral, visual works on offline and online mediums, all your information will be anonymized unless you want to be credited.

I will try to transform these stories into text formats in case you want to delete your Reverb contents or account. That could take some time, so it would be nice to receive a heads up before you delete your Reverb content.

If you change your mind to be included in this moment, you may request for your work to be deleted by sending me an email through seda.ozcetin@umu.se. It would be nice to know why so that i conduct better moments in the future.

The Miro board will be closed to public access after the festival. If you want to stay on the board, please get in touch via email to receive a passcode.

For any comments or questions, please contact me through seda.ozcetin@umu.se.

Thank you so much for your time!

Hope you enjoy this moment!